

第2讲 CiteSpace原理与基础

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《CiteSpace科技文本挖掘及可视化》（第四版）配套课件

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李杰科学网博客: <http://blog.sciencenet.cn/u/jerrycueb>

开放科学计量学学习平台: <https://www.metamatrix.cn/home>

The longer you can look back, the farther you can look forward (回顾历史越久远, 展望未来就越深远)。

汇报提要

1. CiteSpace是什么？ CiteSpace应用现状？
2. CiteSpace核心原理与术语
3. CiteSpace的核心功能与可视化设计
4. CiteSpace可分析的数据源及其数据结构
5. CiteSpace数据分析流程
6. CiteSpace学习推荐资料

1.1 CiteSpace是什么?

CiteSpace全称为Citation Space，是2003年由美国德雷塞尔大学计算与情报学院华人陈超美教授基于JAVA开发的多元与分时的科技文献可视化软件。

该软件经过20余年的发展已经成为世界知名的科技文本挖掘与分析工具。CiteSpace的核心功能就是通过对某“知识域”的科技文本进行可视化挖掘分析，来展示科学的历史发展与结构变化。

陈超美，美国德雷塞尔大学计算机与情报学学院教授。现任国际期刊《Information Visualization》和《Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics》主编，以及《Journal of Data and Information Science》编委。曾先后担任英国布鲁内尔大学客座教授和大连理工大学长江学者讲座教授。研究方向为信息可视化、科学前沿图谱和科学发现理论。发表科技论文200余篇，被引超过13000次。出版著作科学计量学及数据可视化方面的著作近10部，并有多部被翻译成中文。

CiteSpace是什么?
(AI生成)

陈超美教授学术画像

Chaomei Chen

FOLLOW

Professor of Informatics, College of Computing and Informatics, [Drexel University](#).
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[Information visualization](#) [visual analytics](#) [scientometrics](#) [bibliometrics](#) [scholarly communication](#)

TITLE	CITED BY	YEAR
CiteSpace II: Detecting and visualizing emerging trends and transient patterns in scientific literature C Chen Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology 57 (3 ...	7320	2006
Searching for intellectual turning points: progressive knowledge domain visualization C Chen Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences 101 (suppl_1), 5303-5310	2981	2004
Visualizing knowledge domains K Börner, C Chen, KW Boyack Annual review of information science and technology 37 (1), 179-255	2408	2003
The structure and dynamics of cocitation clusters: A multiple-perspective cocitation analysis C Chen, F Ibekwe-SanJuan, J Hou Journal of the American Society for information Science and Technology 61 (7 ...	2087	2010
Science Mapping: A Systematic Review of the Literature C Chen Journal of Data and Information Science 2 (2), 1-40	1930	2017
Emerging trends in regenerative medicine: a scientometric analysis in CiteSpace C Chen, Z Hu, S Liu, H Tseng	1449	2012

Cited by

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	All	Since 2020
Citations	40409	22376
h-index	71	47
i10-index	180	114

Public access

[VIEW ALL](#)

0 articles	24 articles
not available	available

Based on funding mandates

1.2 CiteSpace的应用概貌（全球的用户每日下载情况）

Downloads

287,359

2018-09-02 to 2020-02-28

Countries

Top: CN, at 87%

Operating Systems

Top: Windows, at 93%

1.2 CiteSpace的应用概貌（全球的用户在下载地理分布）

国家/地区	总下载量
China, Mainland 中国大陆	252736
United States	7783
Hong Kong, China 中国香港	3009
Brazil	2396
Turkey	1701
Japan	1634
Taiwan, China 中国台湾	1541
United Kingdom	1458
Singapore	1141
Germany	1086
India	1025
Australia	998
Korea, Republic of	978
Canada	752
Russia	714
Spain	580
France	500
Malaysia	498
Netherlands	434
Indonesia	433

1.2 CiteSpace的应用概貌（应用领域分布）

1.2 CiteSpace的应用概貌（期刊领域分布）

1.2 CiteSpace的应用概貌（应用论文的主题）

2. CiteSpace核心原理

- **哲学基础：** 托马斯·库恩的科学革命的结构给CiteSpace提供了哲学基础。库恩认为，科学的推进是建立在科学革命上的一个往复无穷的过程。这个过程中会出现一个又一个的科学革命，人们的认识通过科学革命而接纳新的观点。
- 库恩的科学革命是新旧科学范式的交替和兴衰。科学认识中会出现危机，而危机所带来的新旧范式的转换都将在学术文献里留下印记。库恩的理论给我们提供了一个具有指导意义的框架，如果科学进程真像库恩所洞察的那样，那我们就应该能从科学文献中找出范式兴衰的足迹。

陈超美，李杰主编. 科学知识前沿图谱与实践论文集/ 陈超美, CiteSpace 的分析原理[C]. 北京：高等教育出版社, 2018.

2. CiteSpace核心原理

核心设计灵感——结构洞： Burt的结构洞和库恩的范式转换在CiteSpace中得到了具体体现。库恩的范式体现为一个又一个时间段所出现的聚类。聚类的主导色彩揭示了他们兴盛的年代。伯特的结构洞连接了不同聚类。

我们可以从中更深入地了解一个聚类如何连接到另一个几乎完全独立的聚类，以及哪个具体文献在范式转换中起到了关键作用。结构洞的思想在CiteSpace中体现为寻找具有高度中介中心性的节点。这样我们不在拘泥于具体论文的局部贡献，而放眼于他们在学术领域的整体发展中的作用。这恰恰是系统性学术综述所追求的飞跃。

其他理论：信息觅食，Kleinberg频率突增算法

陈超美，李杰主编. 科学知识前沿图谱与实践论文集/ 陈超美, CiteSpace 的分析原理[C]. 北京：高等教育出版社, 2018.

ture of DNA (Moffat 1993). Thomas Kuhn developed his ideas on scientific paradigm shifts while working at the nexus of history and physics; yet it would be extremely difficult to look for common principles across paradigms by examining a single paradigm. Once Black and Scholes recognized their formula for options pricing as a physics equation for heat transfer (Black and Scholes 1973, p. 644) they could look for established parallels. Similarly, the Alvarez theory that an asteroid caused the extinction of the dinosaurs emerged from a fortuitous combination of father and son skills in astrophysics and geology (Alvarez 1980). "Some of the greatest achievements in science come from work at the boundaries of disciplines."¹⁷ The difficulty is that it is not always clear beforehand which groups need to share information.

Marshall Van Alstyne, Erik Brynjolfsson (2005) Global Village or Cyber-Balkans? Modeling and Measuring the Integration of Electronic Communities. Management Science. Page 29. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.1050.0363>

2. CiteSpace核心概念：转折点（中介中心性）

中介中心性（Betweenness centrality）是测度节点在网络中重要性的一个指标（此外还有度中心性、接近中心性等）。中介中心性（Betweenness centrality）表示一个网络中经过该节点的最短路径的数量。表示在网络图中，一个节点在多大程度上是图中其他节点的“中介”。在网络中，节点的中介中心性越大，则它在其它节点之间的通信中起到的作用越大。此类节点在网络中起到“沟通桥梁”的作用。在社会网络中，使用中介中心性可以用来识别网络中的“跨界者”（boundary spanners）。

CiteSpace中使用此指标来发现和衡量文献的重要性，并用紫色圈对该类文献（或作者、期刊以及机构等）进行重点进行标注（出现紫圈的节点的中介中心性 ≥ 0.1 ）。中介中心性高的节点往往在连接不同聚类路径的节点上，就是CiteSpace中常提到的术语“转折点”（Turning Point）。

2. CiteSpace核心概念：突发性探测

Burst 检测：用于探测主题、文献、作者以及期刊引证信息的突发性变化。在CiteSpace中使用 Kleinberg, J (2002) 年提出的算法进行检测。突发性文献的意义 (1) 如果一篇论文的引文频次突然呈现急速增长；(2) 这篇论文切中了学术领域要害问题。

扫码视频讲解

Identifies sudden increases or “bursts” in the frequency-of use of character strings over time.

J. Kleinberg. Bursty and Hierarchical Structure in Streams. Proc. 8th ACM SIGKDD Intl. Conf. on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, 2002.
<http://www.cs.cornell.edu/home/kleinber/bhs.pdf>

Börner K, Polley D E. Replicable Science of Science Studies[M]// Measuring Scholarly Impact. Springer International Publishing, 2014:321-341.

2. CiteSpace核心概念：引文年轮

引文年轮（Citation tree-rings）代表着某篇文章的引文历史。引文年轮的颜色代表相应的引文时间，一个年轮厚度和与相应时间分区内引文数量成正比。

2. CiteSpace核心概念：时间切片

时间切片（Time slicing），按照所下载数据的时间范围，对数据进行切分。

2. CiteSpace核心概念： 阈值

第一个值2代表了某个项目（item）出现的次数不低于2次。

中间的2代表两个items之间的共现次数最低要为2。

标准化后的余弦标准化强度不小于0.2。

数据阈值设置的意义：数据分布的幂律分布，使得阈值的设置尽可能地分析重要的信息。

An example power-law graph, being used to demonstrate ranking of popularity. To the right is the long tail, and to the left are the few that dominate (also known as the 80-20 rule).

该功能是对节点出现次数和关系强度进行的筛选。

2. CiteSpace核心概念：研究前沿与知识基础

思考?

什么是文献耦合?
什么是文献共被引?

知识基础是一个有利于进一步明晰研究前沿本质的概念。如果把研究前沿定义为一个研究领域的发展状况，那么研究前沿的引文就形成了相应的知识基础。研究前沿的知识基础是研究前沿在文献中的引用轨迹。

文献耦合 VS 文献共被引

文献耦合分析
Bibliographic Coupling

施引论文A和B是相关的，
因为它们都引用了论文C，
D，E和F

文献共被引分析
Co-Citation

被引论文a和b是关联的，
因为它们都被论文c，d，
e和f引用了。

3. CiteSpace的核心功能与可视化设计

3. CiteSpace可分析的数据源 (DS)

Figure: **Map of the bibliodata landscape**
 Stakeholders are positioned along two axes: Production \leftrightarrow Use (horizontal axis) and Private \leftrightarrow Public (vertical axis). Neither the relative size of a stakeholder bubble nor its position (centre vs. periphery) reflects its importance or centrality. The map shows the position of specific stakeholders vis-à-vis the two defined axes and the vast range of other participants in the field.

3. CiteSpace可分析的数据源 (DS)

Figure 1. Overlap of documents between Scopus and the other data sources.

Figure 2. Breakdown by publication year for all documents in each data source (solid line) and for the overlap with Scopus (dashed line).

Figure 7. Overlap of citation links between Scopus and the other data sources.

Visser, M., van Eck, N. J., & Waltman, L. (2021). Large-scale comparison of bibliographic data sources: Scopus, Web of Science, Dimensions, Crossref, and Microsoft Academic. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 2(1), 20–41. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00112

3. CiteSpace可分析的数据源 (DS)

功能 数据源	合作网络			共现分析			共被引			文献 耦合	双图 叠加
	作者	机构	国家/地区	关键词	术语	领域	文献	作者	期刊		
WoS	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Scopus	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Derwent	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗
CNKI	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
CSSCI	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗
CSCD	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗
RCI	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
KCI	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗

3. CiteSpace可分析的数据源：Web of Science数据结构

Authors

AU Galea, S
Ahern, J
Resnick, H
Kilpatrick, D
Bucuvalas, M
Gold, J
Vlahov, D

co-authorship

Terms

TI Psychological sequelae of the September 11 terrorist attacks in New York City.
SO NEW ENGLAND JOURNAL OF MEDICINE
LA English
DT Article
ID **POSTTRAUMATIC-STRESS-DISORDER**; NATIONAL COMORBIDITY SURVEY; MAJOR DEPRESSION; NATURAL DISASTER; SOCIAL SUPPORT; **OKLAHOMA-CITY**; PREVALENCE; PSYCHOPATHOLOGY; SURVIVORS; SYMPTOMS
AB Background: The scope of the **terrorist attacks** of September 11, 2001, was unprecedented in the United States. We assessed the prevalence and correlates of acute **post-traumatic stress disorder** (PTSD) and depression among residents of Manhattan five to eight weeks after the attacks. Methods: We used random-digit dialing to contact a representative sample of adults living south of 110th Street in Manhattan. Participants were asked about demographic characteristics, exposure to the events of September 11, and psychological symptoms after the attacks. Results: Among 1008 adults interviewed, 7.5 percent reported symptoms consistent with a diagnosis of current PTSD related to the attacks, and 9.7 percent reported symptoms consistent with current depression (with ``current`` defined as occurring within the previous 30 days). Among respondents who lived south of Canal Street (i.e., near the World Trade Center), the prevalence of PTSD was 20.0 percent.

Location

CI New York Acad Med, Ctr Urban Epidemiol Studies, New York, NY 10029 USA. Columbia Univ, Mailman Sch Publ Hlth, Dept Epidemiol, New York, NY USA. Med Univ S Carolina, Natl Crime Victims Res & Treatment Ctr, Charleston, SC 29425 USA. Schulman Ronca & Bucuvalas, New York, NY USA. Bellevue Hosp Ctr, New York, NY 10016 USA.
RP Galea, S, New York Acad Med, Ctr Urban Epidemiol Studies, Rm 556, 1216 5th Ave, New York, NY 10029 USA.
CR 2001, NY TIMES 1226, B2
*AM PSYCH ASS, 1994, DIAGN STAT MAN MENT
*DEP HLTH HUMAN SE, 1999, MENT HLTH REP SURG G
*US BUR CENS, 2000, STF3A DEP COMM BUR C

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SHAH B, 1997, SUDAAN USERS MANUAL
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SHALEV AY, 2000, J CLIN PSYCHIAT S5, V61, P33
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SHORE JH, 1989, J NERV MENT DIS, V177, P681
TUCKER P, 2000, J BEHAV HEALTH SER R, V27, P406
NR 32
TC 179
PU MASSACHUSETTS MEDICAL SOC/NEJM
PI WALTHAM
PA WALTHAM WOODS CENTER, 860 WINTER ST., WALTHAM, MA 02451-1413 USA
SN 0028-4793
J9 N ENGL J MED
JI N. Engl. J. Med.
PD MAR 28
PY 2002
VL 346
IS 13
BP 982
EP 987
PG 6
SC Medicine, General & Internal
GA 534UY
UT ISI:000174608600006
ER

Citations

Year

3. CiteSpace可分析的数据源：Web of Science数据结构

co-occurring burst terms

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SHORE JH, 1989, J NERV MENT DIS, V177, P681

author co-citation

document co-citation

journal co-citation

ACA/DCA/JCA

3. CiteSpace可分析的数据源：数据分析原理

4. CiteSpace的核心功能与可视化设计

地理可视化

文献的共被引聚类 (网络图)

时区图

CiteSpace

山峦图

密度图 (热力图)

圆形视图

期刊的双图叠加

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BEARD AN, 1997, FIRE SAFETY J, V28, P117, DOI	1997	3.7699	2000	2005	[Bar]
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DRYSDALE D, 1999, INTRO FIRE DYNAMICS, V0, P0	1999	5.6049	2001	2005	[Bar]
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HWANG CC, 2005, FIRE SAFETY J, V40, P213, DOI	2005	3.9864	2008	2012	[Bar]
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ARIOZ O, 2007, FIRE SAFETY J, V42, P516, DOI	2007	4.2356	2009	2013	[Bar]
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LAUTENBERGER C, 2009, FIRE SAFETY J, V44, P819, DOI	2009	6.9971	2012	2018	[Bar]
STOLIAROV SI, 2009, COMBUST FLAME, V156, P1068, DOI	2009	5.2846	2012	2018	[Bar]
INGASON H, 2011, J FIRE PROT ENG, V21, P5, DOI	2011	3.9256	2013	2018	[Bar]
CHAOS M, 2011, P COMBUST INST, V33, P2599, DOI	2011	5.3694	2013	2018	[Bar]
INGASON H, 2010, FIRE SAFETY J, V45, P371, DOI	2010	5.9616	2014	2018	[Bar]
DRYSDALE D, 2011, INTRO FIRE DYNAMICS, V0, P0	2011	17.4409	2014	2018	[Bar]
ZHOU XY, 2012, FIRE SAFETY J, V54, P36, DOI	2012	4.4694	2014	2018	[Bar]

文献的突发性探测

文献共被引聚类 (时间线)

网络叠加分析

5. CiteSpace数据分析流程

CiteSpace可分析数据:
 Web of Science核心合集
 Scopus索引数据库
 CSSCI中文社会科学索引
 CNKI中国知网

确定研究目的

选择数据库

数据

数据预处理
 格式WoS

CiteSpace

数据预处理

新建项目
 参数设置

功能及参
 数设置

Start

分时网络合并

可视化界面

网络聚类

聚类命名

突发性探测

可视化

.....

结果研判

结果保存

结果发布

项目命名
 文件加载
 连线设置
 阈值设置

时间切片
 网络类型
 阈值设置
 相似测度
 网络裁剪

5. CiteSpace 数据分析流程

预判和解读提示:

方法: 由浅入深 (地理, 宏观双图叠加, 聚类图, 时间线, 关键词, 被引文献等)
 范围: 从整体到局部
 聚类: 从大到小
 时间: 由远到近
 色彩: 由鲜艳 (重要) 到平淡
 字体: 由大到小
 标签: LSI, LLR, MI
 指标: burst, 中心性, sigma, u180, u2013

6. CiteSpace最新进展 (CiteSpace+大模型)

6. CiteSpace最新进展 (CiteSpace+大模型)

```

CiteSpace
GraphPanel(3950): Cluster Labeling by Titles in progress (Cast: 25%):
LabelSelector: Cluster #15: Processing titles of 1 qualified citers: 1!
LabelSelector: Cluster #11: Processing titles of 1 qualified citers: 1!
LabelSelector: Cluster #9: Processing titles of 2 qualified citers: 2!
LabelSelector: Cluster #7: Processing titles of 1 qualified citers: 1!
LabelSelector: Cluster #6: Processing titles of 5 qualified citers: 5!
LabelSelector: Cluster #5: Processing titles of 8 qualified citers: 8!
LabelSelector: Cluster #4: Processing titles of 3 qualified citers: 3!
LabelSelector: Cluster #3: Processing titles of 10 qualified citers: 10!
LabelSelector: Cluster #2: Processing titles of 12 qualified citers: 10.12!
LabelSelector: Cluster #1: Processing titles of 12 qualified citers: 10.12!
LabelSelector: Cluster #0: Processing titles of 17 qualified citers: 10.17!
Graph: Labeling Cluster #0 ... 0.014 seconds!
Graph: Labeling Cluster #1 ... 0.004 seconds!
Graph: Labeling Cluster #2 ... 0.006 seconds!
Graph: Labeling Cluster #3
Graph: Labeling Cluster #4
Graph: Labeling Cluster #5
Graph: Labeling Cluster #6
Graph: Labeling Cluster #9
Graph: Cluster Labeling (L
Graph: Reusable entities:
Compact Clusters: Time Tak
libpng warning: iCCP: know
libpng warning: iCCP: know
Ollama: gemma:2b processin
Ollama: gemma:2b processin
Ollama: gemma:2b processin
Ollama: gemma:2b processin
llm_load_print_meta: UNK token = 3 '<unk>'
llm_load_print_meta: PAD token = 0 '<pad>'
llm_load_print_meta: LF token = 227 '<0x0A>'
llm_load_print_meta: EOT token = 107 '<end_of_turn>'
llm_load_print_meta: max token length = 93
llm_load_tensors: ggml ctx size = 0.08 MiB
llm_load_tensors: CPU buffer size = 2126.45 MiB
llama_new_context_with_model: n_ctx = 8192
llama_new_context_with_model: n_batch = 512
llama_new_context_with_model: n_ubatch = 512
llama_new_context_with_model: flash_attn = 0
llama_new_context_with_model: freq_base = 10000.0
llama_new_context_with_model: freq_scale = 1
llama_kv_cache_init: CPU KV buffer size = 144.00 MiB
llama_new_context_with_model: KV self size = 144.00 MiB, K (f16): 72.00 MiB, V (f16): 72.00 MiB
llama_new_context_with_model: CPU output buffer size = 3.94 MiB
llama_new_context_with_model: CPU compute buffer size = 508.25 MiB
llama_new_context_with_model: graph nodes = 601
llama_new_context_with_model: graph splits = 1
INFO [wmain] model loaded | tid="31068" timestamp=1722738466
time=2024-08-04T10:27:47.082+08:00 level=INFO source=server.go:622 msg="llama runner started in 4.56 seconds"
[GIN] 2024/08/04 - 10:29:04 | 200 | 1m22s | 127.0.0.1 | POST | "/api/generate"
[GIN] 2024/08/04 - 10:30:21 | 200 | 1m16s | 127.0.0.1 | POST | "/api/generate"
[GIN] 2024/08/04 - 10:35:12 | 200 | 4m51s | 127.0.0.1 | POST | "/api/generate"
[GIN] 2024/08/04 - 10:36:29 | 200 | 1m16s | 127.0.0.1 | POST | "/api/generate"
[GIN] 2024/08/04 - 10:36:56 | 200 | 26.8519479s | 127.0.0.1 | POST | "/api/generate"
[GIN] 2024/08/04 - 10:37:50 | 200 | 54.1438106s | 127.0.0.1 | POST | "/api/generate"
[GIN] 2024/08/04 - 10:38:29 | 200 | 38.966886s | 127.0.0.1 | POST | "/api/generate"
[GIN] 2024/08/04 - 10:38:52 | 200 | 23.5509922s | 127.0.0.1 | POST | "/api/generate"
[GIN] 2024/08/04 - 10:39:17 | 200 | 24.6801214s | 127.0.0.1 | POST | "/api/generate"
    
```

Cluster #0: Domino Effects in Chemical Plants

The largest cluster (#0) has 69 members with a silhouette value of 0.847. The major citing articles of the cluster are:

Coverage	GCS	LCS	Citing Articles
30	7	0	Khakzad, N (2017-JAN) Application of graph theory to cost-effective fire protection of chemical plants during domino effects . RISK ANALYSIS, V37, P16 DOI 10.1111/risa.12712
27	17	0	Khakzad, N (2017-JAN) Application of dynamic bayesian network to performance assessment of fire protection systems during domino effects . RELIABILITY ENGINEERING & SYSTEM SAFETY, V167, P16 DOI 10.1016/j.res.2017.06.004
24	1	0	Jia, M (2017-JAN) Equipment vulnerability assessment (eva) and pre-control of domino effects using a five-level hierarchical framework (flhf) . JOURNAL OF LOSS PREVENTION IN THE PROCESS INDUSTRIES, V48, P10 DOI 10.1016/j.jlp.2017.05.004
23	3	0	Chen, C (2019-JAN) Integrating safety and security resources to protect chemical industrial parks from man-made domino effects: a dynamic graph approach . RELIABILITY ENGINEERING & SYSTEM SAFETY DOI 10.1016/j.res.2019.04.023
22	3	0	Khakzad, N (2018-JAN) How to address model uncertainty in the escalation of domino effects? . JOURNAL OF LOSS PREVENTION IN THE PROCESS INDUSTRIES DOI 10.1016/j.jlp.2018.03.001

Summary: A cluster of articles focusing on vulnerability assessment, cost-effective allocation of safety measures, and emergency response to domino effects in chemical plants.

The most cited members in this cluster are:

- 27 Khakzad N, 2013, RISK ANAL, V33, P292, DOI 10.1111/j.1539-6924.2012.01854.x
- 21 Landucci G, 2009, ACCIDENT ANAL PREV, V41, P1206, DOI 10.1016/j.aap.2008.05.006
- 21 Reniers G, 2013, DOMINO EFFECTS PROCE, V0, P0
- 21 Cozzani V, 2005, J HAZARD MATER, V127, P14, DOI 10.1016/j.jhazmat.2005.07.003
- 18 Cozzani V, 2009, ACCIDENT ANAL PREV, V41, P1216, DOI 10.1016/j.aap.2008.06.002

CiteSpace学习推荐资料

2016.2
First Edition

2017.8
Second Edition

2022.5
第三版

Jie Li

Chao-Mei Chen

科学计量与知识图谱系列丛书

丛书主编: 李 杰

CiteSpace:
Text mining and
Visualization in Scientific Literature (Fourth Edition)

CiteSpace:
科技文本挖掘及可视化
(第四版)

李 杰 陈超美 著

随着信息技术的飞速进步, 可视化应用越来越普及, 今后的学习越来越多地借助各种可视化手段, 视觉器官将发挥前所未有的作用。

可视化方式成为主流学习方式后, 人类的学习效率将大大提高, 有可能带来一场认知革命。

首都经济贸易大学出版社
Capital University of Economics and Business Press

李杰, 陈超美. CiteSpace科技文本挖掘及可视化(第四版)[M]. 首都经济贸易大学出版社. 2025.

CiteSpace常见问题解答

The screenshot shows the CiteSpace website's FAQ page. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for Blogs, Exemplars, Gallery, FAQs, Standard, and Advanced. Below the menu, the 'FAQ' section is highlighted, with a sub-section for '常见问题解答'. A purple button labeled 'Experimental: CiteSpace101 GPT' is visible. The main content area lists four FAQ items, each with a plus sign to its right:

- 1.0 Current Versions 现行版本
- 1.1 What is CiteSpace for? CiteSpace 的作用是什么?
- 1.2 Key Visual Patterns and Features in CiteSpace 可视化展现的动态结构特征及意义
- 1.3 What should I do if I encounter a problem? 遇到问题怎么办?

<https://citespace.podia.com/faq>

The screenshot shows a blog post on ChaomeiChen's personal blog. The header includes the blog title 'ChaomeiChen的个人博客' and a share button. Below the header is a navigation menu with links for 博客首页, 动态, 博文, 视频, 相册, 好友, and 留言板. The main content area is titled '留言板' and contains a comment form with a placeholder text: '您需要登录后才可以留言 登录 | 注册'. Below the form is a '留言' button. The comment list shows four entries:

- [3986] 杨凤娇 2025-1-8 20:03 IP: 36.57.103.*
陈老师您好, 有个问题向您请教。我在共被引期刊导出的前十名中发现最后一名不是期刊, 是一个国际会议INT C REHAB ROBOT, 请问下这是什么情况呢? Citespace在分析期刊的时候会默认分析会议么? 遇到这种情况怎么办呢, 论文里期刊那个部分的三线表里没法填这个国际会议影响因子H指数之类的信息。。。
- [3985] 尚红彦 2024-12-13 22:20 IP: 112.32.39.*
陈老师您好, 我现在在用您的CiteSpace 6.3.R1 (64-bit) basic写一篇文章, 在介绍软件引用的时候, 不知道这个版本的发布地点? CiteSpace version 6.3.1 R1 for Windows, CiteSpace software, 地点, www.citespace.podia.com.占用您宝贵的时间, 非常感谢您
我的回复(2024-12-15 12:43): 引用这篇就可以: Chen, C. (2006) CiteSpace II: Detecting and visualizing emerging trends and transient patterns in scientific literature. Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology, 57(3), 359-377.
- [3984] 于大力 2024-12-11 09:27 IP: 112.231.98.*
陈老师, 非常感谢您的指导! 我使用的版本是6.3.R1 (64-bit) basic, 数据来源是CNKI, 我发现时间切片设置为1年、2年或者更多一点, 生成的图谱差别较大, 对于这个问题您说时间切片的选择取决于所要研究的问题以及这些问题本身的跨度等等特性, 麻烦您再给具体指导一下吗, 比如说大概怎么根据研究问题进行设置, 怎么根据问题跨度来设置, 非常感谢!!!
我的回复(2024-12-15 12:51): 如果一个问题的整个过程只有1-2年, 你选择时间切片是就要考虑分辨率。如果用5年切片就无法充分展现这个短暂的过程。你可以用关键词或引文的burst历史来判断发展速度。如果红线往右漂移的很快, 则应该选择更薄的切片。
- [3983] 于大力 2024-12-9 10:32 IP: 112.231.98.*
陈老师, 非常感谢您百忙之中的回复! 我使用的版本是6.3.R1 (64-bit) basic, 数据来源是CNKI, 在进行作者合作分析时, 发现

<http://blog.sciencenet.cn/u/ChaomeiChen>

CiteSpace学习推荐资料

李杰科学知识... 动态 投稿 52 合集和列表 2 收藏 3 订阅 设置 搜索视频、动态

关注数 16 粉丝数 3581 获赞数 547 播放数 3.6万 阅读数 5495

默认排序 升序排序 编辑

去创作中心添加视频

1 0-CiteSpace对话 32:26 40 6-18

2 0-CiteSpace前言-陈老师 13:35 42 6-18

3 CiteSpace公开课视频：1 科学知识 与科学知识图谱 16:08 1656 2020-5-7

4 2-设计和分析原理-陈老师 44:40 64 6-18

5 3-CiteSpace的设计和分原理-陈老师 23:17 37 6-18

6 4-CiteSpace的分析流程-陈老师 34:24 38 6-18

7 5-CiteSpace经典案例分析流程-陈老师 22:18 16 6-18

8 6-CiteSpace的安装和功能介绍-李 老师 01:05:25 33 6-18

9 7-CiteSpace数据采集及预处理-李 老师 01:07:42 55 6-18

10 8-CiteSpace科研合作网络的分析- 李老师 20:47 18 6-18

11 9-CiteSpace主题和领域的共现分 析-李杰 23:19 16 6-18

12 10-科研合作网络的地理可视化实 操-李杰 16:36 28 6-18

13 11-CiteSpace常见问题解答-李杰 14:26 19 6-18

14 操作演示：Web of Science数据库 简介及数据的可视化.mp4 24:12 36 6-18

15 操作演示：CiteSpace下载、安装及 案例运行-李杰.wmv 12:12 48 6-18

16 操作演示：教育研究期刊分析 06:06 32 6-18

17 操作演示：CNKI数据采集及导 入.wmv 09:36 26 6-18

18 操作演示：CSSCI数据采集及导 入.wmv 06:11 15 6-18

Bilibili视频: <https://space.bilibili.com/508721901/channel/collectiondetail?sid=496360>

CiteSpace理 论与实践

美国德雷塞尔大学/陈超美教授 中国科学院 文献情报中心/李杰 副研究员

主讲教师：陈超美, 李杰 教师团队：共 2 位

课程访问量(PV值): 54485

目录

- 课程介绍
- 教师团队
- 课程章节
- 参考教材
- 免费指南下载
- 教学资源

课程介绍

CiteSpace是在科研大数据背景下设计和开发的，用于进行科学论文数据挖掘和分析的可视化工具。使用CiteSpace能够有效的挖掘科学研究的现状和发展态势，并服务于我们的科学研究和教学活动。本次课程的内容主要包含 CiteSpace对科学研究合作网络的研究（包含了作者的合作、机构的合作、国家/地区的合作）、科学研究研究前沿和知识基础及其研究热点的分析和识别。

教师团队

陈超美 教授 单位：美国德雷塞尔大学

李杰 副研究员 单位：中国科学院文献情报中心

课程章节

1 引言 1.1 对话CiteSpace 1.2 课程介绍 1.3 科学与科学知识图谱	2 CiteSpace设计原理与未来展望 2.1 CiteSpace设计原理 2.2 CiteSpace未来展望 2.3 课外资料：CiteSpace原理	3 CiteSpace分析流程 3.1 CiteSpace分析流程 3.2 CiteSpace分析流程图
4 CiteSpace安装与功能介绍 4.1 CiteSpace下载与安装	5 CiteSpace数据采集与预处理 5.1 科技论文数据采集与预处理	6 CiteSpace数据分析 6.1 CiteSpace合作网络分析

<https://mooc1-1.chaoxing.com/course/212680405.html>

CiteSpace学习推荐资料

Novelty, Uncertainty, and Granularity

CiteSpace学习文献

1. CiteSpace I (转折点) : Chen, C. (2004) Searching for intellectual turning points: Progressive Knowledge Domain Visualization. Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA, 101 (suppl.), 5303-5310.
2. CiteSpace II (概念模型与案例) : Chen, C. (2006) CiteSpace II: Detecting and visualizing emerging trends and transient patterns in scientific literature. Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology, 57(3), 359-377.
3. CiteSpaceIII(聚类命名): Chen, C., Ibekwe-SanJuan, F., & Hou, J. (2010) The structure and dynamics of co-citation clusters: A multiple-perspective co-citation analysis. Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology, 61(7), 1386-1409. 10.1002/asi.21309
4. Discovery Theory (发现理论) : Chen, C., Chen, Y., Horowitz, M., Hou, H., Liu, Z., & Pellegrino, D. (2009). Towards an explanatory and computational theory of scientific discovery. Journal of Informetrics, 3(3), 191-209
5. Structural Variation (结构变异) : Chen, C. (2012) Predictive effects of structural variation on citation counts. Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology, 63(3), 431-449.
6. Dual map overlay (双图叠加) : Chen, C., Leydesdorff, L. (2014) Patterns of connections and movements in dual-map overlays: A new method of publication portfolio analysis. Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology, 65(2), 334-351.
7. 最新案例: Chen, C. (2020) A Glimpse of the First Eight Months of the COVID-19 Literature on Microsoft Academic Graph. Front. Res. Metr. Anal. 5:607286.
8. 最新案例: Chen, C., Song, M. (2019) Visualizing a field of research: A methodology of systematic scientometric reviews. PLoS ONE, 14(10):e0223994.
9. 最新案例: Chen, C. (2017) Science mapping: A systematic review of the literature. JDIS, 2(2), 1-40.
10. 英文图书: Chen, C. (2016) CiteSpace: A Practical Guide for Mapping Scientific Literature. Nova Science Publishers.

李杰, 陈超美. CiteSpace科技文本挖掘及可视化(第四版)[M]. 首都经济贸易大学出版社. 2025.

CiteSpace 电子资源下载

下载地址: <https://zenodo.org/communities/citespace>

1. 陈超美. (2025). CiteSpace经典文献合集. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14985793>.
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17. 李杰. (2025). Introduction to Scientometrics(《科学计量学导论》配套课件). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14872219>

声明：该电子课件为《CiteSpace科技文本挖掘及可视化》的配套电子课件，请合理使用。

科学计量与知识图谱系列丛书 丛书主编: 李 杰

CiteSpace: Text mining and Visualization in Scientific Literature (Fourth Edition)

CiteSpace: 科技文本挖掘及可视化 (第四版)

李 杰 陈超美 著

随着信息技术的飞速进步，**可视化**应用越来越普及，今后的学习越来越多地借助各种可视化手段，视觉器官将发挥前所未有的作用。

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Open Scientometrics Learning Platform
开放科学计量学学习平台

科学计量学理论与工具视频 MOOC for Scientometrics Theories and Tools

开放科学计量学视频号

什么是科学计量学 (AI生成)

CiteSpace
CiteSpace理论与实践
(主讲人: 陈超美、李杰)
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陈超美 科学网博客

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